

ISic1079

I.Sicily inscription 1079

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

decree

Material

stone

Object

cippus

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Phintias

Place of origin (modern)

Licata

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Licata

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140561

1. ἐπὶ Τιμοδ. Γ[.]Ω ὁ δᾶμος τ[ῶ]ν Γελ[ώ]ι[ω]ν.

2.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492707

EDCS 39102236

PHI 140561

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. *Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. Inscriptiones Graecae consilio*

et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV. Berlin.
At 14.0259 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)
1888-. *L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 1959.0288
Carità, C. 1978. *Le iscrizioni di Gela trovate a Licata.* Palermo.

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